

RES4CITY CASE STUDY #1

Templederry Community Windfarm

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Executive Summary

Figure 1. Templederry Community Windfarm - Graphical Abstract

The case study describes the establishment and success of Ireland's first community-owned wind farm. Initiated by community members with a Certificate in Renewable Energy, the project aimed to revitalize a declining area through renewable energy. Despite challenges such as securing funding and obtaining planning permissions, the community set up a wind development company and installed two turbines.

The wind farm's success led to the creation of Community Power (Figure 1), the first community-owned electricity supplier in Ireland, underlining the shared benefits of renewable energy, especially at a local level. The case study highlights the importance of local ownership and involvement in renewable energy projects, such as wind farms, for community revitalization and sustainable energy future.

Abstract

Templederry Community Windfarm, the first and only community owned wind farm in Ireland, became operational in November 2012. The development consists of two 2.3 MW Enercon turbines.

Templederry community is located in County Tipperary on the northern edge of the Slieve Felim mountains. The area suffered from population decline and there were limited local employment opportunities.

The community wind farm project began when four individuals from the community completed a Certificate in Renewable Energy at the then Tipperary Institute and, following from this, sought to explore opportunities for a renewable energy project in the region, as part of the Environmental Protection goal within their Community Development Plan.

Introduction

Templederry community group was established as a result of a number of local individuals commissioning a Development Plan study to ascertain the economic development potential of the parish. The community applied for LEADER funding to develop this Community Development Plan. Once funding was obtained, public meetings were held in four parish centres to engage the wider community in the process and information was circulated to all community groups in the area.

The study report identified renewable energy, including wind, biomass and anaerobic digestion, as a means to achieve social, economic and environmental development for the community. Feasibility studies, funded by the County Enterprise Board and carried out by the Tipperary Energy Agency, were carried out into these three forms of renewable energy (Tipperary Energy Agency, 2023). After the feasibility assessed the pros and cons of each, the group decided on wind energy, as they believed it would be the quickest to develop.

Some of the original objectives for this community renewable energy development project were to generate a substantial amount of energy from renewables, to support the declining rural economy and to demonstrate what can be achieved for communities through the development of such projects. One of the key questions that the group considered before deciding on a project was what return they would like to obtain for

each investor in the project and this decision influenced their thinking on the type and scale of the project.

The group set up a dedicated wind development company, where anyone interested could take shares. The group aimed to raise €30,000 for the original planning application. The original project grouping was established through local community meetings in parish and school halls. This group then sought investors from the local community via an invitation in the parish newsletters and the local paper as well as announcements during local religious services. While initial interest was limited, the group managed to secure investment from 30 members of the local community.

Description of Case Study

The aim of this project for Tipperary Energy Agency was to assist Templederry

Community Group in the development of wind energy in their Community by providing them with the resources to analyse and determine the most appropriate mechanism for the development of wind energy by the community (Tipperary Energy Agency, 2023).

Key Objectives of the project were:

- Identify suitable sites in the community for the development of wind energy;
- Assist the community in the purchase of an anemometer;
- Erect anemometer on site, selected by the community;
- Record and analyse the wind speed data in the area;
- Assist the community in negotiations with wind developers to ensure maximisation of their involvement in wind development;
- Educate the local community with regard to development of renewable energy in the area.

Case Study Solution

Once the dedicated wind energy company was set up, the group began to consider potential turbine locations. The assessment of the potential wind energy resource at any site is a complex task and particularly so for a small community which has no expertise or general knowledge in this area. It was in this regard that the community sought to link with the Tipperary Energy Agency to ensure that this work could be done at a local level and a mechanism could be developed to increase the

knowledge and skills in the local community about renewable energy (Tipperary Energy Agency, 2023). The wind resource was assessed as follows: Tipperary Energy Agency had produced a wind resource map for Co. Tipperary (as part of an EU-funded project). This was assessed to isolate the Templederry community, and the data was overlaid on a local topographical map. This resulted in a total of 20 potential sites being identified. Each site was visited individually and assessed in terms of elevation, ownership, archaeology, proximity of dwellings, grid connection, aspects and openness to prevailing winds and transport access (Tipperary Energy Agency, 2023).

A member of the local authority planning team also helped the group by suggesting a particular hill that was free from designation constraints and which took zones of visual influence (ZVI) into consideration

and therefore would be considered more suitable from a planning viewpoint. The community group accepted this suggestion and, with the help of funding from the European Union (EU) Rural Development programme LEADER1, set up a wind monitoring mast on site.

Once they had determined that the site was feasible for wind energy development, planning permission for three 1.3 MW turbines was sought. The wind farm was granted planning permission and the group then applied for grid connection.

Due to grid capacity issues at the time, the ability to get connection was delayed and it was around 3.5 years before grid connection became possible.

Significant funds were required in order to secure the grid connection (the group needed to pay for 50% of grid connection costs, which were €940,000), which could not be funded by the local

community group. For this project, an Enercon loan and LEADER grant each funded €200,000 to help secure the grid connection. Without this funding, the project could not have gone ahead.

When the grid connection was secured, it was found that the delivery time for turbines would be just over 2 years. Due to these delays, the original planning permission expired and the group needed to reapply for planning permission. This time they applied for two 2.3 MW turbines. While this was eventually granted, a number of objections were lodged to the second application, and it was rejected by the local planning authority. The decision was appealed to an Bord Pleanála and it took over two years before a decision was reached and planning permission was granted.

Once planning permission was received, the community group sought a Power Purchase Agreement (PPA) to sell the

output from the wind turbines. They negotiated with a number of energy companies and reached an appropriate agreement.

In addition to the LEADER grant aid and Enercon loan, the project was financed by a range of other sources including shareholder equity, a business expansion scheme and project finance from De-Lage Landen (a subsidiary of Rabo-Bank).

The community group signed a turbine delivery contract with Enercon. The turbines were delivered on 17th September 2012, were up and running by the middle of November 2012 and were fully tested and commissioned by 1st January 2013. To date, they have been performing better than expected.

This project has had a number of benefits within the local community, many of which will continue to benefit the community into the future.

Some key benefits include:

Complete local ownership of the project, which means that, other than capital and finance costs, the full income will revert to the community group investors.

Specific community-level projects have not yet been funded. However, such projects are envisioned for the future once the project loans have been paid off. The choice of any projects funded and any community benefit they generate will be in full control of the Templederry community group. The community group have indicated that potential future projects that may be considered include low-carbon housing for the elderly, school projects and social housing projects.

From the viewpoint of the community group, having 100% of the profits going to the community is much better than a single developer building a wind farm with only a small percentage going to the community.

Demonstration of what can be achieved when individuals in the community work together, enhancing public acceptance and awareness of renewable energy projects within the community. The community group is considering the development of additional renewable energy projects. Any such projects will benefit from the expertise gathered in the local community. The company that set up the wind farm is now examining other options for renewable energy generation.

While the second planning application in this project had some level of objection (indicating that there was not full community acceptance of the project), now that the project is completed there is a much greater level of interest in renewable energy initiatives throughout the community.

The community group also now has the experience and expertise to help other groups with planning, selecting turbines,

PPA, developing finance packages, etc.

Results and Discussion

It should be noted that given the conditions in relation to wind development in Ireland at the time in terms of price paid per kWh of electricity produced the Templederry region could not be considered to be ideal. There were few areas with average wind speeds above 8.5 m/s and indeed it was projected that the wind speeds in the site selected would be in the region of 6.5-7.5 m/s. However, the community sought to link with relevant lobby groups such as Meitheal na Gaoithe (Irish Wind Farm Co-operative) to seek specific support for community-based projects such as theirs to improve their economic viability.

Templederry Community Windfarm has been generating electricity since 2012 and has led to the development of

Community Power (Community Power, 2023). Community Power is Ireland's first community owned electricity supplier (Community Power, 2023). They are a partnership of community energy groups working for a sustainable energy future for Ireland who grew out of Ireland's first community owned wind farm, Templederry Wind Farm in Co Tipperary, and now are working with Irish communities to develop more renewable energy projects owned by people (Community Power, 2023).

As well as the electricity generated from Templederry Community Windfarm, Community Power are also buying renewably generated electricity from a handful of small and micro hydro and wind generators across Ireland and selling it to their customers to use in their homes, businesses, farms and community buildings (Community Power, 2023).

The mission of Community Power is to support Ireland to run on clean, renewable power, but they also feel people should have a real stake in it, and own it for themselves. They recognise that Ireland's energy system is in crisis, with over 90% reliance on climate-polluting fossil fuels, but many people are struggling to pay high energy bills in cold homes (Community Power, 2023). That's why Community Power is working to make sure the many benefits of generating renewable power are shared by the people and communities of Ireland (Community Power, 2023).

Conclusion and Recommendations

Templederry Community Windfarm is Ireland's first community owned windfarm which has been in operation since 2012 and has since led to the development of Community Power (Community Power, 2023). The project is seen as a success story and is a flagship case study for any local community energy groups interested in developing their own project. However, there has been very few projects of it's kind in Ireland since.

One of the key issues affecting wind farm development is the acceptability by the local community. It is widely thought that this can be overcome by the community getting involved in the wind farm, and benefiting directly from the green electricity being generated. Therefore, community ownership is critical to the future of wind farms in Ireland. One of the key benefits of renewable energy that is often quoted is the ability for these energy sources to be developed at a local level bringing local benefits. However, it is often the case that this particular benefit can often be the most difficult to maximise.

References

- Community Power. (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://communitypower.ie/>
 - Tipperary Energy Agency. (n.d.). Templederry Community Windfarm. Retrieved from <https://tippenergy.ie/our-work/templederry-community-windfarm>
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